

Impact of Thinking Map and Role-Play Instructional Strategies on Performance in Basic Science among Students in Makurdi, Benue State

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Abstract

The study investigated the Impact of Thinking map and Role- play Instructional Strategies on Performance in Basic Science among Students in Makurdi, Benue State. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test and post-test non –equivalent, non-randomized control group design. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level. The population for the study consists of 1,886 upper basic II students from 27 UBE junior secondary schools located in Makurdi metropolis. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw 60 students in two intact classes from two schools for the study. The research instrument used for data collection is called Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT) instrument. The instrument was validated by three experts and the reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Kuder- Richardson formula 20(K- R₂₀) which yielded 0.80. The data collected were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses. The findings revealed that: there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores [$F(1,26) = 0.104$; $p = 0.750 > 0.05$] of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy. The second finding revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores [$F(1,28) = 2.623$; $p = 0.117 > 0.05$] of male and female students exposed to Basic Science using Role play instructional strategies. It was recommended among others that Basic science teachers should employ thinking maps and role play instructional strategies when teaching basic science.

Key words: thinking maps, role play, academic performance and gender.

Introduction

The technological advancement of a nation depends on the level of scientific and technological knowledge of the citizenry where education remains a veritable tool for this attainment and that formed the decision of the federal government to introduce Basic Science at the upper basic level to exposes young learners to the world of science. Basic science is considered the bedrock of all science subjects. It is the subject that prepares students at the upper basic level for the study of core science subjects like Biology, Physics and Chemistry (Ode & Eriba, 2019). The overall objectives of Basic Science curriculum as stated in Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2012) is to enable the learners: develop interest in science and technology; acquire basic knowledge in science and technology; apply scientific and technological knowledge and skills to meet contemporary societal needs, take advantage of the numerous career opportunities provided by science and technology; become prepared for further studies in science and technology among others. In spite of the importance attached to the Basic Science it has observed that the performance of students over the years is low and inconsistent (BECE, 2021).

Performance is the observable or measurable behaviour of a person or an animal in a particular situation usually in an experimental situation Yusuf as cited in Ada, Eriba and Toryem (2020). Students' low performance is generally blamed on poor teaching strategies or methods (Ode, Akpoghol & Otor 2020). Jiya (2011) argued that when teaching is characterized by rote learning, meaningless memorization or verbalism, students learn ineffectively. One among the most striking challenges in BS is that, there has been low and inconsistent students' performance in the results of external examinations in the subject as evident at Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) over the years. Report from Benue State Examination Board

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(BECE, 2021) shows a mean failure of 46.61% and 49.30% in the year 2016 and 2017 respectively. However, in the year 2018, 2019 and 2020 the result showed an increased average score of 54.96%, 63.87% and 59.90% respectively with an inconsistent fluctuation trend. Prominent among the contributing factors responsible for low and inconsistent performance in Basic Science is the predominant use of teacher- centered teaching methods and traditional subject based methods, which in recent times became ineffective (Ode, Akpoghol & Otor 2020).

Effective utilization of appropriate and student-centered teaching strategies like Thinking Maps (TM) and Role Play (RP) may help to improve students' performance in Basic Science. To motivate students, the teacher needs to make science real and relevant by using teaching strategies that will enable students learn Basic Science easily and effectively. Thinking Maps according to Hyerle (2009) is a set of explicit visual representations of thinking processes which fosters life-long learning in students. To DeLorenzo (2011), Thinking Maps provide visual support for the mental processes of diverse learners. The graphic patterns are connected to the cognitive skills whereby they can stimulate how thinking is developed. TMs has also been reported as a "useful tool for helping younger students with the process of building conceptual understandings of disciplinary content and, consequently, promoting their achievement" Abi-El-Mona and Adb-El Khalick as cited in (Ruba & Alaeddin, 2017). TMs therefore if effectively used in Basic Science lessons could positively affect students' performance and promote higher order thinking and helps students become independent long-life learners. TMs also allow students to be more involved in the learning process, "as it forces and encourages them to map out their thought process on paper, which leads to an increase in connections between content and experience (Long & Carlson, 2011)".

Empirically, Alabdulaziz and Alhammadi (2021) who conducted research on the effectiveness of thinking map to improve students' achievement in mathematics observed a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students exposed to thinking maps strategy and those taught using conventional method. Also, Ugbeda (2021) conducted research on the effect of think-pair cooperative learning strategy on secondary school students' achievement and retention in electrochemical in Makurdi metropolis and found that students taught using think-pair cooperative learning strategy achieved higher and retained better than those taught using conventional method and the female outperformed their male counterparts. Role-playing as explained by Rao and Stupans (2012) is the practice of having students take on specific roles and act them out in a case – based scenario for the purpose of learning course content or understanding complex concepts.

Role-Play has been touted as a tool better suited for the needs of today's college students than more traditional teaching methods. According to Maier in Puyate (2017), Role-Play pedagogy has been shown to be effective in reaching learning outcomes in three major learning domains such as affective, cognitive and psychomotor. Westrup and Planander (2013), were of the opinion that by making students take on the role of another person, they practice empathy and perspective taking. This could lead to more self-reflection and awareness on the part of students. Empirically, Zhu (2012) found that role play improves both male and female learners' performance and generally helps students understand what they have learnt in an easy way. Moreso, Sadeghi and Sharifi, 2013, Nair, Yusof and Arumugam, 2014; Aldillah, 2015 and Altun, 2015 in their separate research found that role-play activities can provide a stress-free learning environment where students enjoy the learning process. The findings also showed that role play activities enable students to gain self-confidence and enhance performance.

Puyate and Eniekenemi (2017), investigated the effects of Role-Playing Teaching Strategy and Its effect on academic achievement of students in learning simple blue print reading. The findings from the study revealed that experimental group taught simple blue print reading with role play teaching method performed better than those taught with the lecture method and that there is no significant difference in academic achievement between male and female students taught simple blue print readings using role play teaching method. Gender is another variable that could influence performance. According to Ugwu (2015), gender is regarded as the sex of mentee which is also referred to as the stratification of male and female offering subjects in schools. Given the low and inconsistent academic performance of students, Jack and Japheth ascited in (Jesulowo, Lawal, Bichi, Lawal & Mari 2021) observed that many students' especially female students become less confident in their academic skills and career. According to the authors, poor academic performance of students may also be attributed to factors such as truancy from schools, poverty, economic issues, and teachers' inappropriate use of instructional strategies among others.

Research findings on gender difference in Basic Science students' achievement/performance are few. Moreover, the results of the few available ones are not consistent. For instance, Ode, Agbike, Abah, and Chia (2019) study revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE, Oludipe and Oludipe (2018) found no significant difference, Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender. On the other hand, Ada, Eriba and Toryem (2020) found that, male outperformed their female counterparts taught with simulation in Biology and Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). Moreso,

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Akaayar (2017) and Ode (2018) found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female Basic Science students in their separate studies. The inconsistency of these findings suggests that research on the influence of gender on students' performance in Basic Science and science in general is inconclusive. This implies that more research is needed in this direction and area of study which this study intends to find the effectiveness of TMs and RP with regards to gender.

Objective of the Study

The following objectives were stated for the study:

1. Examine the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy.
2. Determine the mean academic performance scores of male and female students when taught Basic Science using Role Play Academic instructional strategy.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy?
2. What is the difference in mean the academic performance scores of male and female students' taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy and those taught using Role Play instructional strategy.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy and those taught using Role Play instructional strategy.

Methodology

This study adopted the quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test and post-test non –equivalent, non-randomized control design. The choice of this design was due to the fact that, this study used the intact classes so as not to distort the normal academic programmes of the schools involved, due to randomization of subjects to experiment groups. The appropriateness of quasi experimental design for this study was considered on this ground. (Emaikwu, 2012). A population of 1886 students was drawn from all the 27 UBE junior secondary schools located within Makurdi town (Benue State Universal Basic Education Board, 2021). Purposive and simple random sampling technique were used to select two schools for the study. Two intact classes were used for the study with a sample size of 60 Upper-Basic II students from the two schools selected for the study. The selection of intact classes was done using hat and draw method. One intact class each from the two schools was assigned randomly to experimental group one and the second intact class was assigned to experimental group two using thinking map and role play instructional strategies respectively and a psychometric test was carried on forty items in which thirty were accepted and ten were rejected.

The Basic Science Performance Test (BSPT), a 30 multiple choice questions with four options was used for data collection. Pre- test was administered before treatment; post-test was then administered after reshuffling in order to avoid familiarity immediately after treatment was given. The items were delimited to concepts of energy, work, power and energy transformation when work is done. BSPT's section "A" collected students' bio data; while section 'B' generated data on students' academic performance in Basic Science. The instrument was validated by three experts: of the three experts, two were science educators, while the third one is an expert in test and measurement, all from Benue State University, Makurdi. Their inputs were used to improve the quality of the instrument.

The instrument was trial tested using 40 Upper-Basic II students from two schools that were not part of the actual study but had similar characteristics. To determine the reliability coefficient of BSPT, Kuder Richardson formula ($K-R_{20}$) was used and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The instrument was administered by research assistants' understand examination conditions using BSPT and the data was obtained. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using ANCOVA. The choice of ANCOVA was to remove the initial difference between groups since intact classes were used. The decision rule in the null hypotheses was that if the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis will be rejected, but if the p-value is not less than 0.05 the null hypothesis is not rejected.

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Results

The Results are presented according in order of research questions and hypotheses:

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female students taught BS using TMs Instructional Strategy.

S/No	Gender TMs	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Male	9.21	2.485	14.32	5.323	5.11	In favour of female students
2	Female	9.00	2.789	15.00	4.784	6.00	
3		Mean difference				0.89	

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 1 shows the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy. Data in the table also reveals that the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 5.11 and those of female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 6.00. The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy is 0.89 in favour of female students taught Basic Science using Thinking Maps instructional strategy.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students' taught BS using RP Instructional Strategy

S/NO	Gender RP	Pre –test		Post-test		Mean gain	Decision
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev		
1	Male	9.20	2.821	12.70	4.644	3.5	In favour of female students
2	Female	9.19	2.542	15.76	4.929	6.57	
3		Mean difference				3.07	

(Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 2 shows the difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy. Data in the table further reveals the mean gain of male students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is to be 3.50 and those of female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is 6.57 The difference in the mean Academic performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy is 3.07 in favour of female students taught Basic Science using Role Play instructional strategy.

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy.

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Table 3: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students exposed to Thinking Maps Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Decision
Corrected Model	5.563 ^a	2	2.781	.101	.904	.008	Not significant
Intercept	498.841	1	498.841	18.175	.000	.411	
Pretest	2.496	1	2.496	.091	.765	.003	
Gender	2.845	1	2.845	.104	.750	.004	
Error	713.610	26	27.447				
Total	6860.000	29					
Corrected Total	719.172	28					

a. R Squared = .008 (Adjusted R Squared = -.069)
 (Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 3 reveals that $F(1,26) = 0.104$; $p = 0.750 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.004 was obtained for gender meaning that only 0.4% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using thinking maps strategy.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Academic Performance Scores of Male and Female Students exposed to Role Play Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Decision
Corrected Model	66.019 ^a	2	33.009	1.364	.272	.089	Not sig.
Intercept	508.466	1	508.466	21.017	.000	.429	
Pretest	2.509	1	2.509	.104	.750	.004	
Gender	63.465	1	63.465	2.623	.117	.086	
Error	677.401	28	24.193				
Total	7510.000	31					
Corrected Total	743.419	30					

a. R Squared = .089 (Adjusted R Squared = .024)
 (Source: Field work, 2023)

The data in Table 4 reveals that $F(1,28) = 2.623$; $p = 0.117 > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis state that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy is retained. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy. The partial Eta square of 0.086 was obtained for gender meaning that only 8.6% of the Basic Science performance scores can be accounted for the influence of gender in Basic Science class when taught using role play strategy.

Discussion of Findings

Finding from hypothesis one showed that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Thinking Maps instructional strategy. This implies that both male and female students performed high when exposed to thinking maps strategy. This finding agrees with Ode, Agbike, Abah, and Chia (2019) study which revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE. Abuh, (2021) also found that there is no significant difference in mean academic performance among male and female students taught thermal physics using cognitive conflict instructional strategy which is also an innovative strategy. This finding may be possible because thinking maps strategy provide equal

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opportunities to both male and female students as it has been reported to be a useful tool for helping students with the process of building conceptual understanding of disciplinary content and consequently, promoting their performance which made it possible for both male and female to attained high performance. Male and female students are free to share their ideas (thinking) between themselves. However, the finding disagreed with the findings by Akaayar (2017), Ode (2018) and Alabdulaziz and Alhammadi (2021) who found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female basic science students in their separate studies. Ode et al (2019) who found that there is a significant difference in academic achievement of male and female basic science students in Basic Examination Certificate Examination with male students recording higher mean scores than their female counterparts. The finding also revealed that gender has no effect on BS students' academic performance when thinking maps strategy is used.

The finding from hypothesis two indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students exposed to Role Play instructional strategy. This implies that the performance of both male and female students exposed to role play strategy is enhanced. This agrees with Zhu (2012) who found that role play improve learners' performance and generally helps students understand what they have learnt in an easy way. Oludipe (2012) also found that there is no statistical difference in academic achievement of students in respect to gender when exposed to RP. More so, Abah and Chia (2019) study also revealed that there was no significant difference in the achievement of male and female Basic Science students in BECE result. This high and gender free performance could be a result of the involvement of students' active participation in the class as every student's is given an opportunity to make their contribution during group discussions, the intelligent and even the slow learners. Conversely however, this finding disagreed with the findings of Akaayar (2017) and Ode (2018) who found a significant difference between the academic achievement of male and female Basic Science students in their separate studies, Aguele and Uhumniah in Agbidye (2019) also found that the male students achieved higher than the female in science.

Conclusion

The study established that the use of Thinking Maps and Role Play Instructional Strategies enhanced both male and female students' academic performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Basic science teachers should employ Thinking Maps and Role Play instructional strategies in their classroom when teaching Basic Science as the strategies provides opportunities for students to share ideas and understanding.
2. In- service training, seminars and workshops should be organized by the State and Federal Ministries of Education to train Basic Science teachers on how to use Thinking Maps and Role Play instructional strategies in teaching the subject.

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